

Research

Preparation of Melt spun Textile Filament from Waste Plastic Bottle And Its Characterization

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Abstract: This main objective of this project was to produce filament yarn using waste plastic bottles, which are usually thrown away every day in everywhere of the world. For this purpose a fully customized prototype spinneret was built. This machine was capable to melt plastics chips by electric heating system and extrude the PET plastic bottle chips into plastic strings or filament yarns. It was possible to extrude filament of moderate quality. The filament yarns were also dyed using disperses dye. The quality of dyed yarn such as dye ability, color fastness to wash, rubbing, light and perspiration was found excellent. Further tests were carried out to determine other characteristics such as count, strength, elasticity, fabrication ability of the filament yarn. Such a step will also reduce the environmental pollution Bangladesh as well as in Worldwide.

Keywords: Plastic Bottle, PET, Melt Spinning, Recycle, Chips, Heating, Textile

1. Introduction

1.1 PURPOSE & SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

PET is also known as PETE or Polyester. PET stands for Polyethylene Terephthalate and is mostly used for the manufacturing of plastic bottles for liquid or beverage consumption.

Plastics have become a part of our everyday life. In the meeting or a workshop, we often use plastic water bottle. In Dhaka city, about 14 million pieces of polybags are thrown out every day, often ending up in rivers and oceans and causing hazards to marine life. Bangladesh experienced floods in urban areas in 1998 and 2008 where polythene and plastic materials were one of the major causes for the blockage of the drainage systems. A recent report published by Earth Day Network (2018) ranked Bangladesh 10th out of the top 20 plastic polluting countries in the world. Plastic contributes eight percent of the country's waste which is equivalent to 800,000 tones, of which around 200,000 tones go into the ocean and rivers [1].

Globally, one million plastic bottles are purchased every minute. Plastics like PET most likely touch your everyday life. Polyethylene Terephthalate, known commonly as PET or PETE is best known as the clear plastic used for water and soda bottle containers. PET can be identified by looking at the bottom or backs of containers for the #1 resin identification code – a symbol recognized by the #1 in the middle surrounded by “chasing arrows”.

World Economic Forum (2018) found that by 2050, there will be more plastic than fish in the world's oceans due to 13 million tons of plastic ending up in the ocean each year. Plastic bottles are non-biodegradable. Plastic waste is a risk to public health as it enters our food chain, creates congestion problems in drains, causing flooding, ends up in river beds and oceans, depleting ecosystems and marine biodiversity. Production process for plastic produces greenhouse gas, thus contributing to climate change. It is time for Bangladesh, and the world, to introduce alternatives to plastic [1], as Bangladesh is one of the countries in the world to ban plastic. If plastic pollution continues at the current pace, Bangladeshis will be living on islands of plastic, not chars. The time for action is now. Let's beat plastic pollution. We can reduce our plastic pollution by manufacturing of garment products from waste PET bottle.

PET (Poly Ethylene Terephthalate) is the stuff plastic bottles are made of. It's a stable and harmless plastic, which is used most for packaging purposes, because of its vapor barrier and strength properties. In its original state, it's a colorless and crystal clear material.[22]

1.2 POLYESTER/ POLYETHELENE TEREPHTHALATE (PET)

In the meantime the Du Pont Co. had undertaken an independent research program on polyesters and by 1945 had developed a practical method for preparing poly(ethylene terephthalate) (PET) from dimethyl terephthalate and ethylene glycol. The U.S. patent application on PET, based on the work of Whinfield and Dickson, was purchased by Du Pont from Calico Printers, and the patent was subsequently issued with assignment to Du Pont [2, 3]. A plant for the manufacture of PET fiber started up in Kinston, North Carolina, in 1953. After the work of Whinfield and Dickson and the commercial introduction of Dacron and Terrelene polyester fibers, there was extensive further exploration of polyesters for fibers, films, plastics, and other uses. This past and continuing research includes intermediates, catalysts, polymerization processes, and all aspects of production and uses of shaped products.

Although PET is the principal textile polyester fiber worldwide, others have been introduced. One of these is poly (1,4-cyclohexanedimethylene terephthalate), introduced by Eastman in 1958 under the trademark Kodell11 polyester [3, 4]

The polyesters have shown great versatility in textile applications. More polyester fiber is produced and used in the United States and the world than any other single type of synthetic fiber. Nearly 4.2 billion pounds of fiber was produced in the United States in 1979. In addition to general textile uses, PET finds application in non-woven fabrics, fiberfill insulating fiber, ropes and cordage, and in tire cord. A major use is in blends with other fibers such as cotton and wool. With

cotton and rayon, polyester fiber has provided the tensile strength and abrasion resistance which have made the wide use of permanent

1.3 RECYCLED POLYESTER

This process of converting PET into recycled polyester requires much less energy than in the case of normal polyester [8]. In fact it takes 33-53% less energy. Isn't that a huge difference? There are two main advantages to this process:

- Using more recycled polyester reduces our dependence on petroleum as the raw material for our fabric needs.
- Diverting PET bottles for this process reduces landfill, and thus less soil contamination, air and water pollution.
- Another benefit is that the garments created from recycled polyester can be recycled again and again with no degradation of quality, allowing us to minimize wastage. This means garment manufacture could potentially become a closed loop system, polyester could forever be reused and recycled! Something you cannot say for a lot of other fibre. The non-biodegradability of polyester could actually be a good thing, not bad!

We all like cotton, but unless it is organic cotton, we cannot forget the environmental impact of pesticides, chemicals and fertilizers that go into manufacturing the crop. Recycled polyester doesn't require agricultural land, nor does it consume gallons of water like cotton does. Compare it with silk, and you have to agree that no living creatures are harmed during its manufacture, making it a more ethical option. Both of these fabrics also only have a limited life span; they cannot be reused in the same way as polyester and even though they do eventually breakdown they can still take years and years and decompose.

With nearly 653,740 tons of clothes sent to landfill every year, that recycling textiles is becoming increasingly necessary. Textile recycling technology has immense scope where polyester is concerned. Closed loop manufacturing processes are being adopted by more and more manufacturers today, who refine old polyester into new raw material for garments. This technology has nominal waste, consumes limited energy and causes very little pollution. In short, it is environment-friendly.

1.4 PLASTIC BOTTLE

One of the largest recycling efforts of the 20th century happened of course during wars when governments demanded of their people to donate their unused metals, tires and even nylon, but the notion of recycling plastic came only after the environmental revolutions of 1960s. During those years people really started noticing the impact of plastic waste on environment, and started laying groundwork for future recycling efforts. First plastic waste recycling mill in the world was created in Conshohocken, Pennsylvania in 1972, marking the beginning for all future recycling plants. As years went by, government programs and eco-friendly communities slowly started to educate regular people into habit of recycling and forcing manufacturers to start producing easier to recycle plastic. Their efforts came to life during 1980s and 1990s with the adoption of PETE and HDPE plastic, which were designed with recycling in mind. These recyclable plastic products were introduced by Plastic Bottle Institute of the Society of the Plastics Industry and clearly marked on their containers by logo of triangle made of arrows.

1.5 RECYCLED PLASTIC BOTTLE

The process of recycling plastic is not as simple as recycling paper, glass and metals, because the greater number of steps involved for extracting dyes, fillers and other additives that can be found in “virgin” plastic. First step in their recycling is sorting by the type of resin that is in their structure (seven basic types) and in some cases additionally sorted by color. After that, plastic is chopped into small pieces, cleaned to remove debris and small residue, melted down and compressed into pellet. These small pellets are then transported to plastic processing plants where they are introduced into manufacturing process.

Because of the complicated recycling process and unwillingness of people to properly dispose of their unwanted plastic, recycling rates of plastic lag far behind of other items such as paper, glass and metal. In 2008 only 6.5% (2.2 million tons) of post-consumer plastic waste was recycled, 7.7% (2.6 million tons) was burned for energy and 85.5% (28.9 million tons) went to landfills.

2. Materials and methods

2.1 Material Used:

The key material PET (Polyethylene Terephthalate) was collected from the environment. Used up water bottles of transparent drinking water was stored. About 20 to 30 bottles were stored. The Recycle Grade No. of the plastic is #1 which is used to identify PET components. These plastic bottles were cut into small pieces of chip size, washed and cleaned before using.

Figure 1: Chemical structure of Polyethylene Terephthalate (PET)

Polyester fibers take a leading position among all chemical fibers. The unique properties of these fibers are due to the presence of aliphatic and aromatic parts in macromolecular chains and the regular molecular structure. Poly(ethylene terephthalate) (PET) is the predominant polyester used for fiber production, not only because of its good end-use properties and economy of production but in particular because of the ease of physical and chemical modification, suppressing negative and enhancing positive properties of PET. Despite the fact that PET and modified PET fibers were widely investigated, there are still no fully described phenomena of predicting the mechanical behavior and tensile failure based on the structure or manufacturing parameters. One of the main reasons is the complex character of changes during fiber manufacturing and modifications of structure during influence of stress field, temperature, time and environmental factors.

This chapter provides basic information about chemistry, fabrication technology and structure of PET and modified PET fibers. The structure evolution during fiber processing (spinning, drawing and heat treatment) is discussed. The main approaches to the modeling of tensile behavior of polymeric fibers focused on PET are presented. The first part reviews manufacturing techniques of standard polyester fibers and their modifications. The basic routes for synthesizing and treatment of polyesters are discussed. At the same time the influence of internal structure on the mechanical characteristics of polyester fiber is discussed. The influence of degradation processes due to the environmental effects on strength and the fracture processes in PET fibers is described. PET does not crystallize as readily as nylon. The rapidly quenched, undrawn fiber from slow-speed spinning is amorphous. However, as the chains are pulled into alignment during drawing of the fiber, they lock into crystalline register. This can be demonstrated by the fact that, during drawing, the optical orientation factor, giving the overall orientation, increases continuously; but the X-ray diffraction orientation factor indicates axial orientation of the crystals as soon as the crystallization is sufficient to give the diffraction pattern. The crystallinity of drawn fibre is about 50%. There is competition between the rate of orientation as the filament is elongated and the rate of relaxation of the molecules within the attenuated filament. Above about 3000 m/min, thread-

line orientation is high enough to cause crystallization on cooling. This enables the wind-up of a partially oriented yarn (POY), which is stable and suitable for supply to yarn texturing companies. The uncertainty about the structure of the melt-spun polyester fibre is illustrated by Image A, which shows two views of a polyester fibre spun at 5000 m/min by different authors in this book. Admittedly, these were drawn to refer to particular ideas, but nevertheless they give very different impressions of the nature of the structure.

Image A: Two views of the structure of PET filaments spun at 5000 m/min, both from the same book: drawn by (a) Heuvel and Huisman and (b) Shimizu et al. [26].

PET is a fantastic and versatile material, one of the most used types of plastic in the world. Its presence in the 3D printing industry is increasing for its ease of use and strength, but sadly it's not currently made from recycled plastic [14].

Thermoplastic materials become liquid at their melting point (roughly 260° degrees Celsius in the case of PET). A major useful attribute about thermoplastics is that they can be heated to their melting point, cooled, and reheated again without significant degradation [15].

At around 260°C temperature PET melts into a viscous like liquid, which upon coming into contact with air hardens. The hardening process takes some time.

Burning PET is:

At 390° degree centigrade, the burning temperature of PET:

Change in Free Energy: $\Delta G(390^\circ\text{C}) = -5634.4\text{kJ}$ (negative, so the reaction runs)

Change in Enthalpy: $\Delta H(390^{\circ}\text{C}) = -5302.1\text{kJ}$ (negative, so the reaction is exothermic – very exothermic!)[16]

The core idea of this project is to melt the PET material inside an air-tight space with sufficient heat and pressure. After that pressing the melted material through a hole (diameter is about 0.5nm-0.8nm) with extreme pressure.

Figure 2: Relation between pressure of extrusion and flow-out rate

Pressure inside the extruder, for a PET standard extrusion process with a flow rate variation , +10 % [17].

For such arrangement and conditions to be met a custom spinneret was designed and made capable of carrying out such operations.

Trials were carried out to get results,

Actual Trial parameters are noted below.

Table 1

Trial No.	Time for M/c heating in minutes	Stock amount in Grams	Time to reach melting temperature at which point stock started to melt (After stocking)	Chip size (Average in cm)	Time for Cooling(minutes)
1	60	100	10	3	70
2	60	120	20	5	70
3	70	120	25	5	70

Three trials were carried to stock up enough material for testing .Each trial was divided into three parts;

Part 1: Configuration

Due to unavailability of certain measurement devices, machine parameters were gauged and were purely based on assumptions. The heaters capability was checked by trial and error basis and finally it is observed that the machine works properly. It took about 60 minutes for the heater to heat up the machine all the way to the rotating shaft. After then sample chips of PET were found outside the cylinder and it was observed that the chips shrank in size, pointing to the fact that it indeed is capable of melting the chips and convert the chips as filament yarn.

Part 2: Setting Up

Consistency of the process is the key to produce the recycle filament yarn. After the machine was heated up for 60 minutes and then chips were placed inside the machine for melting. This time chips were put inside the cylinder and melting was observed for a certain time. It was also observed that the machine can be considered functional when there the surrounding environment of the machine temperature gets higher. Each time the rotating shaft was pulled out to check the condition of the chips inside the cylinder with utmost care, when a viscous state was confirmed the procedure was carried to the next step i.e. Pressing/Extruding.

Part 3: Operation

Machine was heated by heater for 55 minutes and About 100 grams of chips were put inside the machine and the rotating shaft was used to airlock the cylinder to catalyze the melting process. After 10 minutes the rotating shaft was used to apply pressure on the chips inside the cylinder and

melted chips were extruded as filament yarn by manually applying pressure with the rotating shaft. The filaments were carefully collected and wrapped around a roller.

Fig 3: Output Filaments after operation

3. Conclusion

3.1 ACCUMULATED RESULT & CHARACTERIZATION:

The resulting filament had 1mm-1.2mm diameter and uniformity was fair to the naked eye. It could be stretch by hand, very elastic and fair to good strength. Maximum of 2 feet of the extrusion filament was recorded.

Figure 4: Extruded Filaments from PET Bottle

The key feature of the filaments were tested such as, Strength, Elongation, count, Tensile strength, dye ability etc.

Microscopic image and image of filament after dyeing with disperse dye. A sample of 0.001g or 1mg was taken and tested.

- a. Strength Test: We require a large number of tests to be performed in less time and with higher efficiencies and accuracy levels. To meet this requirement USTER Technologies

produces the USTER TENSORAPID/USTER TENSOJET testing machine, which is frequently used for measuring the single yarn strength.

- b. Tensile Strength Test: By single yarn method, the tensile testing of yarns is done in accordance with ISO 2062 and ASTM D2256. These tests are used to determine the breaking force, elongation, and toughness properties of the yarn. The breaking tenacity, a ratio of the breaking force to yarn linear density, is also a common property for evaluating the strength of a yarn's material and for comparison and validation purposes.
- c. Count: ASTM D 1059-01 & 2260-03, Yarn Count, Denier Count, & Filament Count of Yarns [18]

Table 2: Elongation And Tensile Strength Test Results (average result by several tests)

Strength	Elongation	Presley Index/PI (Load in pound/Bundle weight in mg)	Tensile Strength (g/Tex) 5.36*PI	Count (Tex) Sample length=19 inch Weight=1mg
2.2Kg or 4.84lb	1%	4.84	25.942	2.07

Here's some microscopic view of the recycled filament yarn.

Figure 5: Strand showing unevenness and un-uniformity due to uneven force of extrusion method and manual extrusion process thus affecting count variation.

Figure 6: Strand showing Small cracks on the surface contributing to the low strength and elongation

Figure 7: Strand showing the result of Disperse dyeing at low concentration (less than 1%) Dye penetration and extent of fixing

d. DYEING RESULT

After Dyeing with 2% disperse blue following results were found:

The colors i.e. disperse dye stuffs were very easily absorbed for the synthetic nature of the filament. It was noted that any deep shade could be easily applied to the filament.

Some drawbacks are the lack of dye absorption during low shade percentage and depth of shade.

e. FASTNESS TEST RESULT

The test method by which this test is carried out is AATCC 107-1991 or ISO 105 E01.

This method is to assess the degree of cross staining which may occur when garments are left in contact when damp. The test measures the resistance to water of any colored textiles. Color fastness to water

After carrying out the fastness test procedure described before in Project Design it was found out that the gray scale rating for the Filament was 4/5. Which is excellent.

3.2 EMPHASIS

So it is indeed possible to extrude a filament using only day to day waste PET material. In future, the test will be carried out using capable measuring devices to record the parameters. The use of certain chemicals i.e. Solvents which dissolve PET can be used along with the Machine , which is hoped to reduce the melting time and develop good uniformity to the filament.

Filaments extruded from PET and PP bottles chips by using melt spinning, it is chosen because melt spinning is the most convenient and economic method for polymer fiber manufacturing at industrial scales. The extruded stream cool and solidify into continuous filaments and subsequently wound onto spool. Filament shape can be modified by changing spinneret. Different cross-sectional shapes of filaments have different reflection i.e trilobal-shaped filaments reflect more

light and give attractive sparkle to textiles. By using melt spinning staple and continuous filaments have been extruded and it's a low investment achievement, as plastic bottles are waste materials and machine is also consuming low energy. Till now the filaments of modified machine's is the most progressive work of plastic recycling and further textile fashionable wearing's also will be mostly latest progress of this project.

Globally, one million plastic bottles are purchased every minute. Plastics like PET most likely touch your everyday life. Polyethylene Terephthalate, known commonly as PET or PETE is best known as the clear plastic used for water and soda bottle containers. PET can be identified by looking at the bottom or backs of containers for the #1 resin identification code – a symbol recognized by the #1 in the middle surrounded by “chasing arrows”.

World Economic Forum (2018) found that by 2050, there will be more plastic than fish in the world's oceans due to 13 million tons of plastic ending up in the ocean each year. Plastic bottles are non-biodegradable. Plastic waste is a risk to public health as it enters our food chain, creates congestion problems in drains, causing flooding, ends up in river beds and oceans, depleting ecosystems and marine biodiversity Production process for plastic produces greenhouse gas, thus contributing to climate change. It is time for Bangladesh, and the world, to introduce alternatives to plastic [20].

We can reduce our plastic pollution by manufacturing of garment products from waste PET bottles.[20]Spinning is a novel process making stable yarn and filament yarn. Different types of spinning for filament yarn: wet, dry, dry jet-wet, melt, gel, and electro-spinning. By the melt spinning process we can make filament yarn from PET bottles.

Filaments are extruded from PET and PP bottles chips by using melt spinning. It is chosen because melt spinning is the most convenient and economic method for polymer fiber manufacturing at industrial scales. The extruded stream cool and solidify into continuous filaments and subsequently wound onto spool. Filament shape can be modified by changing spinneret. Different cross-sectional shapes of filaments have different reflection i.e. trilobite -shaped filaments reflect more light and give attractive sparkle to textiles. By using ASTM and ISO methods this extruded filaments characteristics has determined .Staple and continuous filaments has extruded by using melt spinning process and the savings made by utilizing low-cost raw materials for recycled products are usually completely eaten up by complex collection and preparation processes. It's a low investment achievement, as plastic bottles are recycling and machine is also consuming low energy. Nevertheless, recycling can still generate attractive profits, as customers are increasingly willing to pay higher prices for sustainable and environment-friendly products. The growing interest in ecological yarns has been driving the creation of new and highly intended massive. Further treatment process like dyeing, finishing, garments making and so other additional processes will be susceptible and that will ensure this project's commercial uses. Till now the filaments of modified machine's is the most progressive work of plastic recycling and further textile fashion wear also will be mostly latest progress of this project. Further study may prepare fabric by using filaments which is the output of this research.

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Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

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